

EDUCATION, UPBRINGING, AND THE IDEAL HUMAN CONCEPT IN THE WORKS OF CENTRAL ASIAN THINKERS (9th-12th CENTURIES)

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the exploration of free thought, personal development, and individual freedom in the works of Central Asian thinkers during the 9th to 12th centuries. The ideas and concepts presented by Eastern thinkers in this field are analyzed in terms of their significance and relevance, both to the Western world of that period and to the present day.*

Keywords: *scholar, ethics, perfection, ideological, civilization, unity, compassion, national heritage, enlightenment, spiritual culture, spiritual values, scientific heritage, soul, spirit, creator, builder, philosophical-gnoseological foundation.*

Introduction

At a video conference on January 19, 2021, led by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, regarding "Fundamental Improvement of the System of Spiritual and Educational Work," he spoke about elevating spirituality, stating: "If the economy is the body of a society's life, then its soul and spirit are spirituality. Since we have decided to build New Uzbekistan, we will rely on two strong pillars. The first is a powerful economy based on market principles. The second is a robust spirituality grounded in the rich heritage and national values of our ancestors" [1].

Indeed, instilling the heritage of our ancestors and national values in the minds of young people is one of the essential tasks. It is known that the works of great scholars who lived and created in Central Asia during the 9th to 12th centuries—such as Al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, and Ibn Sina—include achievements in philosophy, law, religion, science, and norms of ethics, as well as collections of aesthetic, historical, and literary works, all of which constitute the spiritual heritage of our people. Today, this scientific-philosophical legacy is of great importance in shaping a spiritually developed individual, fostering moral development, and deeply influencing young people's psychology.

It should be noted that our scholars' valuable insights on the spiritual and moral perfection of individuals have retained their relevance and significance to this day. The moral principles, ideas on knowledge, and reflections on individuals and society from our thinkers are not only national heritage but also a spiritual wealth that could occupy a vital place in the spiritual life of humanity. Fully benefiting from these resources, introducing them to the younger generation, and utilizing them in education foster qualities of humanity and patriotism among the youth, helping them find their place in society and contribute to the country's progress.

Literature Review and Methodology

The development of philosophy is directly linked to the progress of human society. A comprehensive and in-depth study of the scientific, philosophical, and socio-political works of our thinkers who lived and created in Central Asia during the 9th to 12th centuries is of great

significance. In advancing philosophical education and furthering the development of our country, today's "New Uzbekistan," the achievements and experiences gained from studying the legacy of our scholars are invaluable.

In modern civilization, understanding the historical progress of humanity and the advancement of scientific knowledge holds great importance. In this regard, scholars like Thomas P. Flint, Michael C. Rea, N. I. Konrad, M. N. Boltaev, and William Chittick, among others, have paid particular attention to this issue in their works [2].

In research conducted by Uzbek scholars, the philosophical views of thinkers such as Al-Farabi, Ibn Rushd, Ibn Sina, and Beruni have been studied in detail based on primary sources. Uzbek philosophers and other researchers have thoroughly illuminated the significant contributions made by these great scholars to the history of philosophical knowledge development [3]. In our view, simply repeating the perspectives of past ancestors will not be enough to develop a philosophy that aligns with the transformations occurring in society and the consciousness of individuals today. This requires awareness of innovations in global philosophy, independent thinking, and a focus on specific approaches.

Result. It is well known that the 9th to 12th centuries in our history are referred to as the "Renaissance period" of Central Asia. It would be appropriate to cite the words of Russian scholar and academic N.I. Konrad regarding the development of Central Asian culture and science: "Let us first turn our attention to the Muslim world, particularly to the Central Asian Muslim world during the 9th to 12th centuries. It is known that during these centuries, the greatest flourishing of science, philosophy, and enlightenment for that era occurred here. It is also known that Al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Al-Khwarizmi, Beruni, Al-Farghani, and other great contemporaries of that time established the direction of scientific and philosophical thought. They assimilated the ancient philosophical and scientific heritage of the ancient world and referred to all the sources of the great civilizations that were linked to their people's historical fate. Central Asia was a crossroads of the most important sources of human civilization in ancient times and represented one of the centers of this civilization. Therefore, in the 9th to 12th centuries, the leading representatives of science and philosophy from the Central Asian world—true humanists—created new teachings and new enlightenment in their principles, taking steps through their own 'Middle Ages' as they bridged the ancient world with their era" [4]. Thus, during this period, our scholars significantly advanced in the fields of science and knowledge, surpassing others.

According to historical records, starting from the 9th century, the long-occupied Iberian Peninsula by the Arabs transformed into one of the most advanced states in the world. In Andalusia, productive forces strengthened, economic ties with Western and Eastern countries expanded, city life and urban culture flourished, and trade and craftsmanship developed. All of this served as a foundation for the flourishing of Arab culture in the West, including philosophy, represented by prominent figures like Ibn Bajjah (died 1138), Ibn Tufayl (1110-1185), and Ibn Rushd (1126-1198).

In this way, the ideas of perfection, happiness, unity, and love—common to the developed Arab-Muslim East—found expression in the teachings of Arab-Spanish philosophers. Ibn Bajjah, Ibn Tufayl, and Ibn Rushd became prominent representatives of this movement. The philosophical and scientific concepts of these scholars were particularly influenced by Al-Farabi's philosophy. The first of these philosophers is known for his materialistic interpretation of Aristotle's philosophy; the second, Ibn Tufayl, was strongly influenced by Neoplatonism and created the

philosophical work “The Tale of Hayy ibn Yaqzan”; the third, Ibn Rushd (Averroes), developed a teaching that unified the entire Arab philosophical culture and marked a significant stage in the history of universal philosophy.

Al-Farabi describes in his treatise “On What One Must Know Before Studying Philosophy” the level of purity that each person seeking to acquire theoretical knowledge must achieve in their morals and ethics: “Before studying philosophy, you must purify yourself from desires and passions to such an extent that you are left with aspirations not for mundane and carnal pleasures, but for perfection. This purification of ethics can be achieved not only through words but also through genuine actions. After this, it is necessary to purify the self, soul, and spirit, which protects one from errors and misguidance and leads to the understanding of the path of truth” [5].

Additionally, Al-Farabi discusses perfection in his work “The Essence of Plato's Laws,” where he defines the concept of “nobility” in relation to perfection. He states that a noble person is not noble for their beauty, strength, frailty, health, or weight, but for adhering to customary behaviors that are in accordance with laws and a dignified way of life. Al-Farabi also emphasizes the various paths to truth, noting: “Philosophy and religion are different paths to the truth that leads to happiness” [6].

Abu Rayhan Beruni associates being knowledgeable and educated with ethics and refinement. In his worldview, the issue of ethics embodies the fundamental qualities of a person. According to Beruni, intellectual abilities arise based on people's daily needs, while ethical matters emerge and develop inextricably linked to historical progress and interpersonal relationships. In his words, a person is a constructive and creative force on Earth. He also defines the positive and negative aspects of humanity. For example, the scholar extols virtues such as goodness, honesty, nobility, kindness, compassion, friendship, and community spirit. He emphasizes that every person who embodies these virtues is capable of achieving anything and can bring invaluable benefits to their people and homeland. Conversely, qualities such as dishonesty, wickedness, competition, greed, envy, rudeness, theft, slander, hypocrisy, self-importance, flattery, and intrigue are condemned as vices [7].

The great thinker Abu Ali Ibn Sina considers mastery of science and knowledge to be the criterion for achieving human perfection. In his view, an educated person is brave, wise, and courageous. His principles in education indicate that teaching should progress from simple to complex, that activities should be appropriate for the age of maturity, that education should be conducted in groups, and that when imparting knowledge, the interests and abilities of the youth should be taken into account. He emphasizes the importance of combining physical activities with education. It is valuable that these requirements align with modern educational principles. His views on education and upbringing promote ideas such as equipping youth with true knowledge, developing their logical thinking abilities, and cultivating the capacity to apply their acquired knowledge in practice.

In the Eastern countries, the emergence of social and legal thought created a foundation for the widespread dissemination of statehood ideas. In the works of our thinkers, the highest aspirations of civic legal thought, ideals of equality, brotherhood, the just king, and teachings about the perfect state that leads to happiness and prosperity found not only philosophical but also legal expressions. During this period, a new perspective on the state and society developed based on legal thinking, leading to a new interpretation of the rights and duties of the state, society, and every citizen. Especially in the quest for the best forms of government and the best structures of

state, the general statements about the divine will of kings in the Middle Ages were replaced by the ideal of a perfect state based on equality and justice, which inspired thinkers. Consequently, there was an increased focus on legal, moral, ethical, and political philosophy.

The ideas of humanism and enlightened thinking, which express the overall direction of the Eastern Renaissance's progressive spiritual culture and reflect the spiritual development of the individual, have been substantiated in various aspects, especially from theoretical-epistemological and scientific perspectives. As the philosophical-epistemological basis of humanism, the doctrine of rationalism emerged. The emergence of humanistic ideas, the achievement of moral maturity, being educated, and moral perfection were considered possible only through intellect and the acquisition of knowledge. Ethics is elevated to a higher level only when it is based on reason, moral knowledge, professional skills, and the study of science. Thus, reason is emphasized as the source of truth, and knowledge and enlightenment are identified as the factors of progress.

With the increasing prominence of the rationalist direction in spiritual culture, the theme of reason gains special significance in the philosophy of the Eastern Renaissance. Thinkers analyze reason from two aspects: as a natural quality of each individual and as a continuous development of intellectual knowledge characteristic of humanity. The intellectual capacity, as an inseparable quality of man, is divided into two: theoretical and practical reason. From the perspective of the continuous development of human intellectual knowledge, reason deepens to reach an active level of intellect based on various stages of understanding the essence of existence and things, ultimately enriching human knowledge about the world and leading to eternity. "The eternity of reason is the eternity of humanity; the results and achievements of human reason belong to eternity". Such a theory serves as the epistemological foundation of humanism, which venerates humanity and proves the infinite power of human intellect and, through it, the importance of acquiring knowledge and enlightenment as vital means to achieve happiness and prosperity.

Ibn Sina and Al-Farabi created a number of works dedicated to the possibilities of human intellect, the classification of sciences, and virtues, significantly contributing to the development of the science of logic, especially regarding the forms and laws of thinking.

Attention was drawn to the intrinsic connection between the art of reasoning and the culture of speech, leading to the high development of rhetoric.

The issues of logic and rhetoric emerged from the essential requirements of rationalist thinking, while the doctrine of rationalism formed the epistemological principle of the broader humanistic direction.

Conclusion

Based on the thoughts of our esteemed scholars mentioned above, it is worth emphasizing that a person possesses the ability to distinguish between emotional and moral demands, and this ability gradually becomes a characteristic of their personality. In the formation of a person, the external environment and the people surrounding them play a particularly important role.

This external environment and these people influence not only a person's understanding of the world but also contribute to the development of their good or bad traits.

Our scholars have pointed out the need to be careful in raising children within the family, stressing the importance of keeping them away from bad habits and harmful environments. After all, a person primarily develops within the family. Thus, the leading ideas of Eastern Renaissance philosophy were pantheism, rationalism, and humanism.

The humanistic ideas that emerged from the foundations of pantheism and rationalism ultimately connect to utopian concepts of achieving happiness and well-being for humanity, ideal self-realized individuals, and perfect social systems. The Eastern Renaissance, particularly during the periods of the First and Second Renaissance in Central Asia, marked one of the greatest achievements in the development of social and philosophical thought.

These ideal concepts have been the age-old dreams of our peoples and are finding their expression in the life of our people today in the era of independence. The progress in developing a humanistic, democratic, and free civil society, enhancing spirituality, and nurturing a well-rounded generation is a vivid testament to this. The implementation of the principle "Strength lies in knowledge and intellect" is clear evidence of this progress.

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